

The Analysis of Word Formation in Movie “Wonder” and Its Application in Teaching vocabulary

Amelya Baiti Nur'aini¹, Juita Triana², Luana Fogli³

{amelya.baiti@gmail.com¹, trianajuita77@gmail.com², Leonide2003@gmail.com³}

English Education Program, Universitas Muhammadiyah Purworejo¹²
Liceo Classico Scientifico Linguistico Tivo Livio, Italy³

DOI: 10.37729/scripta.v8i2.702

Abstract. The aims of this research are to find out word formation in the movie entitled “Wonder” and to describe the application of word formation in movie “Wonder” to teach vocabulary. This research belongs to a descriptive qualitative research. The object is the movie entitled “Wonder”. The data of this study is word formation processes in the movie. To collect the data, the writers do some steps. Those are watching the movie, reading the movie script, and identifying the word formation processes. In analysing the data, the writers conduct some steps: identifying word formation processes in the utterances used by the main characters, classifying the data into types of word formation based on George Yule’s theory, and applying the finding to teach vocabulary. The result of this research shows that there are 148 word formations that are classified into ten types of word formation: 53 of compounding (36%), 5 of coinage (4%), 23 of borrowing (16%), 2 of blending (1%), 8 of clipping (5%), 3 of backformation (2%), 5 of conversion (4%), 2 of acronyms (1%), 45 of derivation (30%), and 2 of multiple processes (1%). The finding of this research can be applied in teaching vocabulary.

Keywords: Word formation; Movie; Wonder; Teaching vocabulary

1. Introduction

Human beings are social creatures that rely on communication to deal with one and another in their lives. In communication, people need language to express their ideas, feelings, and emotions. English is one of the languages which is widely used in the world. It is important to be mastered because most of the current international communication is delivered through English. However, English is not an official language in most countries. It is the language most often taught in various situations as a foreign language.

Vocabulary is one of the crucial components in learning English as a foreign language. Vocabulary is the key to communicate to other people and to express ideas or opinion clearly and easily [1]. Vocabulary itself concerns with words and meanings. It is the matter of the word choice that is used to express ideas or opinions either in written or in spoken English. Mastering vocabulary makes us able to speak English in various kinds of topic. Mastering vocabulary also allows us to develop the four language skills [2]. However, many learners have difficulties in vocabulary. Most of them have limited number of vocabularies. It is also hard for them to memorize the meaning of the words. It makes the learners difficult in choosing the appropriate meaning of the words based on the context.

Dealing with learning vocabulary, people also learn many parts of linguistics. One of them is morphology. Morphology concerns about word structure and word formation. Word formation is one of the discussions of morphology about the process of producing a new word with different meaning [3]. The processes might be from the old words to the new uses without changing the meaning or it may completely create new words [4]. Learning word formation would assist learners to expand their vocabulary mastery [5].

The phenomenon of word-formation process can be occurred in the various media such as textbooks, advertisements, video cameras, computers, songs, movies, etc. From those media, movies have more interesting impression than the other media. Movie is an audio-visual communication that can include various messages such as education, information, and entertainment. The use of movie in teaching and learning process can attract the learners’ attention from a method that is always monotonous. By

watching a movie, especially English movie, learners not only can get an entertainment but also can improve their vocabulary mastery.

One of the interesting movies is a movie directed by Stephen Chbosky entitled “Wonder”. *Wonder* is a drama movie produced based on a novel with the same title written by R.J. Palacio. This movie tells about a 10-year-old boy, Auggie, with a rare medical facial deformity named “mandibulofacial dysostosis”. There are a lot of new vocabularies in this movie that might be formed through a process of word formation. Those new vocabularies can be thought to students so they can enrich their vocabulary mastery.

Referring to the explanations above, the writers want to investigate the word formation by using this movie as the data source of this research. In order to treat the topics more precisely and effectively, the researcher will only discuss about word formation by analyzing the utterances used by the main characters in “Wonder” movie. The researcher will also describe the application of the result to teach vocabulary. The result of this research is expected to give contribution in improving students’ vocabulary mastery. Likewise teachers can consider it as an additional reference material in teaching linguistics, especially word formation. Teachers can also make teaching learning process more interesting by using movie as their teaching media.

There are some researches that have been done related to the topic of word formation. The first research conducted by [6] discusses word formation process in film script *The Adventures of Tintin*, while [7] searches the formations of word in Andrea Hirata’s *Rainbow Troops*. The similarity between the previous studies and this research is that the data is about word-formation processes. The difference with this research is that this one focuses on the application of word formation in teaching vocabulary.

2. Literature Review

The writers take theories as a foundation to conduct the research. The theory used is related to word formation.

1.1 Word Formation

Word formation can be defined as the process of producing a new word with different meaning. Plag as cited in [7] defines word formation as a process of creating new words on the basis of already existing words, including the addition and subtraction of phonetic (or orthographic) material. [8] defines word-formation processes (mechanism) as the study of the processes whereby new words come into being in a language. The processes are forming new words from the use of old words to the new uses.

[8] states that there are some of the basic processes by which new words are created. The types of word formation processes will be explained as follows:

1) Coinage

Coinage is the invention of totally new terms. The most typical sources are invented trade names for commercial products that become general terms (usually without capital letters) for any version of that product. The examples are *aspirin*, *nylon*, *vaseline* and *zipper*; *kleenex*, *teflon*, *tylenol* and *xerox*.

New words based on the name of a person or a place are called eponyms. When we talked about a *hoover* (or even a *spangler*), we were using an eponym. Other common eponyms are *sandwich* (from the eighteenth-century Earl of Sandwich who first insisted on having his bread and meat together while gambling) and *jeans* (from the Italian city of Genoa where the type of cloth was first made). Some eponyms are technical terms, based on the names of those who first discovered or invented things, such as *fahrenheit* (from the German, Gabriel Fahrenheit), *volt* (from the Italian, Alessandro Volta) and *watt* (from the Scot, James Watt).

2) Compounding

Compounding is a combining process of two or more words together to produce a new single form. Common English compounds are *bookcase*, *fingerprint*, *good-looking*, *low-paid*, *fast-food*, and *full-time*.

3) Borrowing

Borrowing is the process of producing new word by taking over the words from other languages. The examples are *croissant* (French), *dope* (Dutch), *lilac* (Persian), *piano* (Italian), *pretzel* (German), *sofa* (Arabic), *tattoo* (Tahitian), *tycoon* (Japanese), *yogurt* (Turkish) and *zebra* (Bantu).

4) Blending

Blending is a combining process of two separate forms to produce a single new term by taking only the beginning of one word and joining it to the end of the other word. Some examples of blending are the

term *smog* (smoke + fog), *smaze* (smoke + haze), *gasohol* (gasoline + alcohol), *brunch* (breakfast + lunch), *telecast* (television + broadcast), and the *Chunnel* (channel + tunnel).

5) Clipping

Clipping occurs when a word of more than one syllable is reduced to a shorter form. The examples are *fax* (facsimile), *gas* (gasoline), *ad* (advertisement), *bra* (brassiere), *cab* (cabriolet), *condo* (condominium), *fan* (fanatic), *flu* (influenza), *perm* (permanent wave), *phone*, *plane* and *pub* (public house). English speakers also like to clip each other's names, as in *Al*, *Ed*, *Liz*, *Mike*, *Ron*, *Sam*, *Sue* and *Tom*.

6) Backformation

Backformation defined as a process of reducing a word of one type (usually a noun) to form a word of another type (usually a verb). The examples of backformation are *television* (from 'televise'), *donate* (from 'donation'), *emote* (from 'emotion'), *enthuse* (from 'enthusiasm'), *liaise* (from 'liaison') and *babysit* (from 'babysitter'). Indeed, when we use the verb *backform* (*Did you know that 'opt' was backformed from 'option'?*), we are using a backformation.

7) Conversion

Conversion is a change in the function of a word, as for example when a noun comes to be used as a verb (without any reduction). A number of nouns such as *bottle*, *butter*, *chair* and *vacation* have come to be used, through conversion, as verbs: *We bottled the home-brew last night*; *Have you buttered the toast?*; *Someone has to chair the meeting*; *They're vacationing in Florida*.

The conversion can involve verbs and phrasal verbs becoming nouns, with *guess*, *must*, *spy*, and *to print out* as the sources of *a guess*, *a must*, *a spy*, and *a printout*. Some verbs, such as *see through* and *stand up*, can also become adjectives, as in *see-through material* or *a stand-up comedian*. Or adjectives, as in *a dirty floor*, *an empty room*, *some crazy ideas* and *those nasty people*, can become the verbs *to dirty* and *to empty*, or the nouns *a crazy* and *the nasty*.

8) Acronyms

Acronyms are new words formed from the initial letters of a set of other words. The examples are *ATM* ('automatic teller machine'), *CD* ('compact disk'), and *VCR* ('video cassette recorder') where the pronunciation consists of saying each separate letter. More typically, acronyms are pronounced as new single words, as in *NATO*, *NASA*, *PIN* or *UNESCO*. These examples have kept their capital letters, but many acronyms simply become everyday terms such as *laser* ('light amplification by stimulated emission of radiation'), *radar* ('radio detecting and ranging'), *scuba* ('self-contained underwater breathing apparatus') and *zip* ('zone improvement plan') code.

9) Derivation

Derivation can be defined as a word-formation process by adding affixes which create a new form, new meaning and can be changing the word class. There are three kinds of affixes from derivation. Affixes that have to be added to the beginning of the word are called prefixes. The examples of prefixes are *un-*, *mis-*, *pre-* which appear in words like *unhappy*, *misrepresent*, and *prejudge*. Other affixes that have to be added to the end of the word are called suffixes. Some examples of suffixes are *-ful*, *-less*, *-ish*, *-ism*, and *-ness* in words *joyful*, *careless*, *boyish*, *terrorism* and *sadness*. The last kind of affixes is infix which means affix that is incorporated inside another word. Infix is not normally used in English, but found in some other languages. The examples of infixes are *Hallebloodylujah!*, *Absogoddamlutely!*, and *Unfuckinbelievable!*.

10) Multiple processes

Multiple processes is possible to trace the operation of more than one process at work in the creation of a particular word. For example, the term *deli* seems to have become a common American English expression via a process of first borrowing *delicatessen* (from German) and then clipping that borrowed form. If someone says that *problems with the project have snowballed*, the final word can be analyzed as an example of compounding in which *snow* and *ball* were combined to form the noun *snowball*, which was then turned into a verb through conversion.

1.2 Teaching Vocabulary

Teaching a foreign language means teaching its components, one of which is vocabulary. Vocabulary itself concerned with words and meanings, as [9] state that vocabulary is the knowledge of the meanings of words. Field, in [10], states that vocabulary is defined as the single words which are easily translated from one language to another language. [11] says that vocabulary can be defined, roughly, as the words we teach in the foreign language. It can be concluded that vocabulary is the basic component of language which concerned with words and its meaning, and it may be used to facilitate students in learning foreign language.

Linse, in [12], states that young learners' vocabulary development is an important aspect of their language development. The more words students know, the easier they will understand the foreign language. [13] says that teaching vocabulary can help learners to build up knowledge of words in any way that will enable them to use the language efficiently and successfully. It means that teaching vocabulary is considered as one of the most important parts of teaching English as a foreign language.

There must be some problems appear in teaching and learning vocabulary process. [14] indicate that teaching vocabulary may be problematic because many teachers are not confident about the best practice in vocabulary teaching and at times do not know where to begin to form an instructional emphasis on word learning. Many teachers have problems how to teach students in order to gain satisfying results. According to [15], the teachers should prepare and find out the appropriate techniques, which will be implemented to the students. A good teacher should prepare himself or herself with various and up-to-date techniques. By having various techniques, it is expected the teaching and learning process would not be monotonous and it may gain satisfying results.

3. Research Methodology

This research belonged to descriptive qualitative research. According to [16], qualitative research approaches collect data through observations, interviews, and document analysis and summarize the findings primarily through narrative or verbal means. [17] states the purpose of qualitative research is to understand something specifically, not always looking for the cause and effect of something and to deepen comprehension about something that studied. The data used in this research was words in the utterances spoken by the main characters in movie "Wonder". [18] states that source data on the research is subject from where data can be gained. Lofland in [19] also state that the main data sources in qualitative research is words and actions, the rest is additional data such as documents and others. The source of this research was taken from the movie "Wonder". The instrument in this research was the writers themselves who act as planners, decision data analyzer, interpreter and also the reporting the results of the research.

[20] states that without knowing the techniques of collecting data, the researchers will not get the data which meet the standard of set in data. In this research, the writers did some steps to collect the data. Those were watching the movie, reading the movie script, and identifying the word formation processes. In analyzing the data, the writers conducted some steps: identifying word formation processes in the utterances used by the main characters, classifying the data into types of word formation based on George Yule's theory, and applying the finding to teach vocabulary.

4. Result

From the movie "Wonder", the writers found 148 word formations that can be classified into 10 types. Types of word-formation processes used in movie "Wonder" are presented on the table below.

Table 4.1 The Word Formation Found in Movie "Wonder"

No.	Types of Word Formation	Total	Percentage
1.	Coinage	5	4%
2.	Compounding	53	36%
3.	Borrowing	23	16%
4.	Blending	2	1%
5.	Clipping	8	5%
6.	Backformation	3	2%
7.	Conversion	5	4%
8.	Acronyms	2	1%
9.	Derivation	45	30%
10.	Multiple processes	2	1%
	Total	148	100%

According to the table above, it can be concluded that there are ten word-formation processes happened in movie "Wonder". The table also indicated that the most dominant type of word formation is compounding which contains 36% from 148 data of word formation processes. The writers also found 5 of coinage (4%), 23 of borrowing (16%), 2 of blending (1%), 8 of clipping (5%), 3 of backformation (2%), 5 of conversion (4%), 2 of acronyms (1%), 45 of derivation (30%), and 2 of multiple processes (1%).

5. Discussion

The discussion of types of word formation used by the main characters in movie “Wonder” will be presented as follows:

a. Coinage

Some examples of coinage found in the movie will be explained as follows:

- 1) “Well, on my *Xbox*.” (5/CNG/AU/00:01:34)

The word *Xbox* is a brand of video game created by Microsoft. It represents a series of video games consoles. *Xbox* was first introduced in United States in November 2001.

- 2) “I love *Minecraft*, science and dressing up for Halloween.” (6/CNG/AU/00:01:36)

The word *Minecraft* is a name of a sandbox video game. The game was developed by Mojang Studios and was officially released in November 2011.

- 3) “The incubator. *Bunsen burners*.” (45/CNG/JL/00:08:41)

Bunsen burner is laboratory equipment that produces a single open gas flame, which is used for heating, sterilization, and combustion. The word *Bunsen* is named after the inventor, Robert Bunsen.

- 4) “And the *Smarties*?” (91/CNG/AU/00:50:15)

Smarties is a brand of food product, that is colour-varied sugar-coated chocolate. *Smarties* is originally introduced by H.I. Rowntree & Company since 1937, and then currently produced by Nestlé. *Smarties* are oblate spheroids that come in eight colours: red, orange, yellow, green, blue, mauve, pink, and brown.

- 5) “I’m not saying poison or anything, but just little *Benadryl*...” (97/CNG/JS/00:56:06)

The word *Benadryl* is a brand name of antihistamine medications. It is used to stop allergies, including diphenhydramine, acrivastine, and cetirizine. *Benadryl* has been manufactured by Johnson & Johnson since 1946.

b. Compounding

In this research, the writers find some compounding words as follows:

- 1) “Eat *ice cream*. Ride my bike.” (2/CMP/AU/00:01:28)

The word *ice cream* derives from Noun + Noun. *Ice cream* is a cold sweet food made from frozen milk, sugar, and a flavor.

- 2) “They’ve helped me to breathe, to see, to hear *without* a hearing aid, ...” (16/CMP/AU/00:02:52)

The word *without* derives from Preposition + Adverb. *Without* means not having or doing something, or lacking of something.

- 3) “So this is our *homeroom*. ...” (34/CMP/JL/00:07:22)

Homeroom derives from Noun + Noun. It means the classroom session in which a teacher records attendance and makes announcements. It can also be called registration or planning period. The concept is used in schools around the world.

- 4) “Well I know it’s hard, but you have to *understand* that ...” (49/CMP/IS/00:10:43)

Understand derives from Preposition + Verb. It means to know the meaning of something, whether situation or message that someone says.

- 5) “*All right*, I’ll let you have all my candy.” (92/CMP/OV/00:50:21)

All right derives from Adjective + Adjective. The word *all right* in this context is used to show that something agreed or acceptable. The other meaning of the word *all right* is to say that something is satisfactory, good enough, or safe.

c. Borrowing

The writers will explain some examples of borrowing words as follows:

- 1) “Via and I have been best friends since *kindergarten*.” (105/BRW/MR/01:01:30)

The term *Kindergarten* comes from German “kinder-garten”. *Kinder* means children, meanwhile *garten* means garden. Therefore, *Kindergarten* means a garden of children, a place for the children aged 5 in their first year of school.

- 2) “Who was his old *boss*.” (108/BR/MR/01:01:59)

The term *Boss* derives from Dutch “baas”, from Middle Dutch “baes” that means “master of a household, friend”. Nowadays, *Boss* means the person who is in charge of an organization and who tells others what to do.

- 3) “Well, um, she was *whimpering*.” (126/BR/OV/01:13:05)

The term *Whimper* derives from German “wimmern” that means to whimper, moan. *Whimper* means (especially of an animal) to make a series of small, weak sounds, expressing unhappiness or pain.

- 4) “Step right up to witness Earth’s greatest mystery, the *volcano*.” (136/BR/JL/01:25:11)

Volcano comes from Italian “volcano” that means burning mountain. *Volcano* is a mountain with a large circular hole at the top through which lava (= hot liquid rock) gases, steam and dust are or have been forced out.

5) “And we all deserve a standing *ovation* at least once in our lives.” (148/BR/AU/01:44:37)

Ovation derives from middle French “ovation” or directly from Latin “ovationem” that means a triumph, rejoicing. *Ovation* is a situation when a crowd of people express great enjoyment and/or approval of something with loud and long clapping.

d. Blending

The writers find two blending words as follows:

1) “But *none* of them have made me look ordinary.” (17/BL/AU/00:02:59)

The word *None* is blended from “No” + “One”. *None* is categorized into pronoun.

2) “My mom still doesn't think I can use a *MetroCard*.” (67/BL/OV/00:29:36)

The word *MetroCard* comes from “Metropolitan” + “Card”. Metropolitan is related to a large city. *MetroCard* is a magnetic stripe card that is used for the primary payment on transportation in the New York City area, such as subway, transit buses, and train. The card was launched in 1992 and operated by Metropolitan Transportation Authority (MTA).

e. Clipping

The writers find some clipping word processes as follows:

1) “Eat ice cream. Ride my *bike*.” (3/CL/AU/00:01:28)

The word “bicycle” is shortened by deleting two syllables to become “bike” only. “Bicycle” is a two-wheeled vehicle that you sit on and move by turning the two pedals.

2) “I know my family loves me, but ever since my *grandma* died,” (63/CL/OV/00:27:38)

The word “grandmother” is shortened become “grandma”. *Grandma* means the mother of our father or mother.

3) “In a *sec*.” (71/CL/JW/00:36:44)

The word *Second* is reduced to become *sec*. *Second* in this context means a very short period of time.

4) “So you do the *math*.” (77/CL/IS/00:43:21)

The word *Math* is clipping. It derives from Mathematics that is shortened by deleting the last three syllables.

5) “Do you think the *vet* can fix her?” (127/CL/AU/01:13:14)

The word *Vet* is also categorized as clipping. *Vet* comes from the word Veterinarian. Veterinarian means a person with a medical degree trained to take care of the health of animals.

f. Backformation

The writers find three backformation processes as follows:

1) “*Prepare* for blastoff.” (53/BF/NT/00:13:39)

The word *prepare* is formed by deleting the suffix –ion from the word “preparation”. There is also a change of class function of word from noun to become verb.

2) “Precepts can help *motivate* us.” (58/BF/BRW/00:16:10)

“Motivation” is shortened to become *motivate* by deleting the suffix –ion. There is also a change of class function of word from noun to become verb.

3) “So I think I can *imagine* what started the fight.” (124/BF/TM/01:09:40)

Imagine comes from the word “Imagination” by deleting the suffix –ion. The word “Imagination” is reduced to form a verb.

g. Conversion

In this research, the writers find five conversion words as follows:

1) “I *auditioned* for Annie on Broadway.” (35/CNV/CHR/00:07:35)

Audition comes from class of noun which means a short performance to show someone ability and suitability for a particular play, film, show, etc. The word *audition* can be changed into different function as verb which means to make someone do a short performance to show his/her ability and suitability for a particular play, film, show, etc. The verb *audition* in this case is added by suffix –ed because the utterance is in the past tense. However, it would not change the base form.

2) “just *picture* where you wanna be.” (54/CNV/AU/00:14:28)

The word *picture* comes from class of noun which means a drawing, painting or photograph, or a situation described in a particular way. In this case, the word *picture* is changed into different function as verb which means to imagine something.

- 3) "They study theatre in the fall and do a *play* in the spring." (64/CNV/JS/00:29:01)

Play derives from class of verb which means to spend time doing an enjoyable and/or entertaining activity. In this case, the word *play* can be changed into different class as noun which means to act the role of somebody in a theatre or on television.

- 4) "Because I want some nice friends for a *change*." (95/CNV/SUM/00:55:21)

The word *change* comes from class of verb which means to make or become different. In this case, the word *change* is changed into different function as noun which means something different, or the result of something becoming different.

- 5) "But I could sure use some *help* right now." (117/CNV/MR/01:03:58)

Help derives from class of verb which means to make it easier or possible for somebody to do something by doing something for them or by giving them something that they need. In this case, the word *help* is changed into different function as noun which means the fact of being useful.

h. Acronyms

The writers find two acronym words as follows:

- 1) "Mrs. Pullman, so good to see you again." (24/ACR/TM/00:04:50)

Mrs. stands for "Mistress" which is a title used before the surname or full name of a married woman without higher or honorific or professional title.

- 2) "I'm Mr. Tushman." (25/ACR/TM/00:04:57)

Mr. is formed from "Mister" which means a title used before the surname or full name of a man without higher or honorific or professional title.

i. Derivation

Some examples of derivation words will be showed as follows:

- 1) "I'm pretty much *totally* and completely petrified." (23/DRV/AU/00:04:07)

The word *totally* derives from root "total" which means being the final number of people or things when they have all been counted. In this case, the word "total" is changed into class of adverb by adding the suffix -ly, which is used to emphasize a clause or statement.

- 2) "Wow! This *reminds* me of my guess spot on Law & Order." (41/DRV/CHR/00:08:06)

Remind derives from the word "mind" which is added by the prefix -re. *Remind* means to put someone in mind of something. There is also a change of class function of word from noun to become verb.

- 3) "Just trying to *lighten* the mood." (59/DRV/NT/00:21:38)

The word *lighten* derives from "light" + -en. "Lighten" in this case means to make something relaxed and less serious. There is also a change of class function of word from noun to become verb.

- 4) "She fell *asleep*." (69/DRV/NT/00:30:34)

Asleep derives from "sleep" which is added by the prefix a-. The meaning of "asleep" is being in a state of sleep. There is also a change of class function of word from verb to become an adjective.

- 5) "It's none of your *business!*" (86/DRV/AU/00:48:15)

Business derives from "busy" which is added by the suffix -ness. "Business" in this case means a situation or activity, often one that you are giving your opinion about. There is also a change of class function of word from adjective to become noun.

j. Multiple Processes

There are two multiple processes found in the "Wonder" movie and they will be showed as follows:

- 1) "I cannot *home school* him forever." (18/MP/IS/00:03:07)

Home school is a word that having multiple process. First is having compounding process between *home* and *school* as *home school*. Second is having conversion process by changing the class function of word from noun to become verb.

- 2) "I auditioned for Annie on *Broadway*." (36/MP/CHR/00:07:35)

Broadway is also formed from a multiple process. First is having compounding process between *broad* and *way* as *Broadway*. Then, in this case, the word *Broadway* comes from a name of a famous theatre in Midtown Manhattan, New York City. This is called coinage process.

To apply the result of this research, the writers suggest English teachers to conduct some steps in teaching vocabulary; 1) Teachers explain about the definition and the types of word formation, 2) Teachers divide the class into several groups, 3) Teachers instruct students to watch movie "Wonder" then analyze the word formation in their group, 4) In the group, students analyze types of word formation

processes on the utterances used in the movie, and 5) Students present their discussion result in front of the class.

6. Conclusion

Based on George Yule's theory, there are 148 words of word formation found in movie "Wonder" that are classified into ten types of word formation. It consists of 53 of compounding (36%), 5 of coinage (4%), 23 of borrowing (16%), 2 of blending (1%), 8 of clipping (5%), 3 of backformation (2%), 5 of conversion (4%), 2 of acronyms (1%), 45 of derivation (30%), and 2 of multiple processes (1%). The most dominant type of word formation found in movie "Wonder" is compounding which consists of 53 words (36%) from total 148 words. Compounding is very common in languages, including in English. Therefore, no wonder compounding becomes the most dominant type of word formation found in movie "Wonder".

The result of this research can be applied to teach vocabulary at senior high school. In future, teaching vocabulary, especially in word formation, can apply more other movies or other sources to provide various learning media to the learners.

7. References

- [1] Mohammad Fakhruddin, E. S. Masykuri, K. Sholeh, and U. Faizah, "Analysis Varied Style of Conversation by Phone in Indonesian Teaching Learning," *EAI*, no. 5, Feb. 2020, doi: [dx.doi.org/10.4108/eai.28-9-2019.2291063](https://doi.org/10.4108/eai.28-9-2019.2291063).
- [2] R. Nurhadi and E. S. Masykuri, "Symbol Meaning and Dialectic Perspectives on Social Media," presented at the Proceedings of the 1st Borobudur International Symposium on Humanities, Economics and Social Sciences (BIS-HESS 2019), Magelang, Indonesia, May 2020. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.200529.234>.
- [3] E. Sunjayanto Masykuri, "The Non-Observance of Cooperative Principle in The Comic-Strip The Adventure of Tintin," Malang, 2014, vol. 1, pp. 118–120.
- [4] E. Sunjayanto Masykuri, "the Use of Code-Switching in Javanese Art Performance Done by Students of SMPN 1 Kesesi Kabupaten Pekalongan," presented at the The 2nd ELTiC, Universitas Muhammadiyah Purworejo, Indonesia, 2016.
- [5] T. Jampi, P. Dewi, and E. S. Masykuri, "The Grammatical Error Analysis Found in Students' Composition," *Lensa: Kajian Kebahasaan, Kesusastraan, dan Budaya*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 218–233, Dec. 2020.
- [6] T. Purwaningtyas, "A Morphological Analysis of Word Formation Process in Film Script 'The Adventures of Tintin,'" State Islamic College of Ponorogo, 2016.
- [7] A. Novita, "Word Formation in Andrea Hirata's Rainbow Troops," State Institute for Islamic Studies Langsa, 2017.
- [8] G. Yule, *The Study of Language*, Third. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2006.
- [9] E. H. Hiebert and M. Kamil, *The Teaching and Learning of Vocabulary*. 2005.
- [10] N. Pachler, *A Practical Guide to Teaching Modern Foreign Languages in the Secondary School*. New York: Routledge, 2007. doi: 10.4324/9780203968017.
- [11] P. Ur, *A Course in Language Teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2009.
- [12] A. Awaludin, "Techniques in Presenting Vocabulary to Young EFL," *Journal of English and Education*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 11–20, 2013.
- [13] L. Cameron, *Teaching Languages to Young Learners*. 2001. doi: 10.1017/cbo9780511733109.
- [14] J. I. Berne and C. L. Z. Blachowicz, "What Reading Teachers Say About Vocabulary Instruction: Voices From the Classroom," *The Reading Teacher*, vol. 62, no. 4, pp. 314–323, 2008, doi: 10.1598/rt.62.4.4.
- [15] A. Susanto, "The Teaching of Vocabulary: A Perspective," *Jurnal KATA*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 182–191, 2017, doi: 10.22216/jk.v1i2.2136.
- [16] M. G. Lodico, D. T. Spaulding, and K. H. Voegtli, *Methods in Educational Research : from Theory to Practice*. Jossey-Bass, 2006.
- [17] L. J. Moleong, *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif*. 2009.
- [18] S. Arikunto, *Prosedur Penelitian : Suatu Pendekatan Praktik*. 2010.
- [19] L. J. Moleong, *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif*. 2017.
- [20] Sugiyono, *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. 2016.